

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of L-cysteine by pyridinium bromochromate in perchloric acid medium

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Abstract : The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of L-cysteine by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) in perchloric acid medium was studied spectrophotometrically at 30 ± 0.1 °C. The reaction is first order dependent on [PBC]. The order of the reaction is less than one with respect to [acid] and fractional order with respect to [cysteine]. The main product of the reaction is cysteic acid. Further, no effect of added chromium(III) was observed. A plausible mechanism was proposed involving complexation between PBC and cysteine. Thermodynamic parameters for the rate determining step of the reaction, E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were computed using linear least squares method and are found to be 19.75 ± 1.30 kJ mol⁻¹ and -57.17 ± 4.51 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Keywords : Oxidation of L-cysteine, pyridinium bromochromate, kinetics, mechanism.

Introduction

The oxidation of sulfur containing amino acids like cysteine has been studied extensively from the point of view of the structure of partially oxidized intermediates and also mechanistic details. Many investigations focused on the oxidative degradation of biologically important thiols, such as cysteine, which is essential to the tertiary structure of many enzymes and proteins. The cysteine oxidation pathway depends significantly on both the nature of the oxidant and the reaction conditions (such as pH).

Literature survey reveals that oxidation of cysteine was carried out by hexacyanoferrate(III) in presence of ethylenediaminetetra-acetic acid (EDTA)¹, vanadium(V)^{2,3}, 2,6-dichlorophenol-indophenol (DCPI)⁴, μ -oxobis [aquabis (2,2'-bipyridine)] ruthenium(III)⁵, tris(oxalato)-cobaltate(III)⁶, chloramine-T and bromamine-T⁷, hexachloroiridate(IV)⁸, Corey's reagent⁹. To probe the mechanism of oxidation of this sulphur containing amino acid further, the author carried out its oxidation with PBC.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by the addition of a known excess of pyridinium bromochro-

mate to known amount of cysteine at 30 °C in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium and after 12 h the residual [PBC] in each case was determined spectrophotometrically at 350 nm. The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to correspond to the equation.

The main product of oxidation was identified as cysteic acid.

The product analysis was carried out by adopting the following procedure :

A reaction mixture containing 0.01 mol dm⁻³ cysteine, 0.5 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid and 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ pyridinium bromochromate in a 50 ml solution was allowed to stand at room temperature. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was extracted with diethyl ether.

The product was confirmed by IR and Mass spectral analysis.

IR spectrum (CHCl₃) ν_{max} of 3421.5 cm⁻¹, 1634.86 cm⁻¹ stretching frequencies are for -COOH, while 1465.43 cm⁻¹, 1218.43 cm⁻¹ and 1095.92 cm⁻¹ stretching frequencies are for -SO₃H respectively (Fig. 1).

Mass spectrum m/z 212.2 amu ($m + H_2O + 23$) corresponds to cysteic acid monohydrate (Fig. 2). In line with the above observations, the product obtained for the oxidation of cysteine by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) was confirmed as cysteic acid existing in the form of cysteic acid monohydrate.

Effect of ionic strength :

At constant concentrations of reactants and with other conditions constant, the ionic strength was varied from 0.6–1.5 mol dm^{-3} by varying the concentration of $NaClO_4$ it was found that ionic strength had no significant effect on the rate of the reaction.

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of cysteic acid.

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of cysteic acid.

Effect of chromium(III) :

The effect of added chromium(III), on the reaction was studied while keeping all other concentrations constant. It was observed that added chromium(III) did not have any significant effect on the pseudo-first order rate constant.

Test for free radicals :

The reaction mixture, to which a known quantity of acrylonitrile scavenger had been added initially, was kept in an inert atmosphere for 1 h at room temperature. When the reaction mixture was diluted with methanol no precipitate of polymer resulted, suggesting that there is no participation of free radicals in the reaction.

Effect of pyridine :

The effect of added pyridine, on the reaction was studied by varying the concentration of pyridine while keeping all other concentrations of reacting species constant. It was observed that addition of pyridine had no effect on the rate of the reaction, which proves the stability of pyridinium bromochromate in aqueous perchloric acid medium.

Effect of PBC :

At constant $[H^+]$ with the [cysteine] in excess, the plot of log (absorbance) versus time is linear, indicating a first order dependence of rate on [PBC]. The concentration of PBC, was varied in the range from $0.5-1.7 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ (Table 1) at a constant concentration of cysteine and acid. The unit order is also confirmed by non-variation of pseudo-first order rate constants with increasing [PBC].

Table 1. Effect of [PBC], [cysteine] and $[H^+]$ on the pseudo-first order rate constant (k')

[PBC] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Cysteine] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
0.5	1.0	0.5	2.33
0.7	1.0	0.5	2.20
1.0	1.0	0.5	2.13
1.2	1.0	0.5	2.13
1.5	1.0	0.5	2.16
1.7	1.0	0.5	2.13
1.0	0.5	0.5	1.43
1.0	0.7	0.5	1.88
1.0	1.0	0.5	2.03
1.0	2.0	0.5	2.60

Table-1 (contd.)

1.0	3.0	0.5	3.45
1.0	4.0	0.5	3.82
1.0	1.0	0.3	1.65
1.0	1.0	0.4	1.83
1.0	1.0	0.5	2.12
1.0	1.0	0.6	2.31
1.0	1.0	0.7	2.50
1.0	1.0	0.8	2.95

Effect of cysteine :

The substrate [cysteine], was varied in the range from $0.5-4.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³ at four different temperatures 25, 30, 35, 40 °C and keeping the concentration of all other reactants constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants were found to increase with increase in the concentration of cysteine and the plot of log k' versus log [cysteine] was found to be linear with a slope of 0.52 at 30 °C. It indicates fractional order dependence with respect to cysteine. Further formation of 1 : 1 complex between cysteine and pyridinium bromochromate was proved kinetically by a Michaelis-Menten plot, i.e. a non-zero intercept of the plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[cysteine]$. Similar plots were obtained experimentally when [cysteine] variations were carried out at 25, 30, 35, 40 °C.

Effect of $[H^+]$:

In order to study the effect of $[H^+]$ on the rate of the reaction, kinetic runs were carried out keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant and varying the $[H^+]$ with perchloric acid. The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained from the log (absorbance) versus time plots show that the rate of the reaction increases with increase in $[H^+]$. Further when the logarithm of k' was plotted against the logarithm of $[H^+]$, a linear plot was obtained with a slope of 0.54 indicating fractional order dependence with respect to $[H^+]$ (Fig. 3).

In the present experimental conditions ($[H^+] = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³), PBC exists mainly in the form of HPBC. The results suggest that HPBC reacts with cysteine forming a complex, which decomposes in the rate-determining step to give an intermediate, chromium(IV) species and a product RSOH. In a further step Cr^V reacts with RSOH giv-

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k'$ versus $\log [H^+]$ (order with respect to $[H^+]$).

ing final products Cr^{III} and cysteic acid. The results can be accommodated in the form of following mechanism.

$$\text{Rate} = k[C]_e = kK_2[HCys]_e[HPBC]_e \quad (7)$$

$$= kK_1K_2[HCys]_e[PBC]_e[H^+]_e \quad (8)$$

The rate equation derived for the above mechanism is

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK_1K_2[Cys]_t[PBC]_t[H^+]_e}{1 + K_1[H]_e + K_1K_2[Cys][H^+]_e} \quad (9)$$

This rate equation explains the observed first order dependence with respect to $[PBC]$ and fractional order dependence with respect to $[cysteine]$.

Since,

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[PBC]_t} = k' = \frac{kK_1K_2[Cys]_t[H^+]_t}{1 + K_1[H^+]_t + K_1K_2[Cys]_t[H^+]_t} \quad (10)$$

Taking reciprocals on both sides of the eq. (10) gives,

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[Cys]} \left\{ \frac{1}{kK_1K_2[H^+]} + \frac{1}{kK_2} \right\} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) predicts the plots of $1/k'$ versus $1/[cysteine]$ should be a straight line with a positive intercept on y-axis. Similar plots (Fig. 4) were obtained experimentally when $[cysteine]$ variations were carried out at 25, 30, 35 and 40 °C. It is also possible to calculate the values of k from the corresponding intercepts of the plots $1/k'$ versus $1/[cysteine]$. The values thus obtained are given in Table 2. The activation parameters of the rate-determining step, E_a and ΔS^* were computed using linear least squares method and the values were found to be $19.75 \pm 1.37 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-57.17 \pm 4.51 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[cysteine]$ at four different temperatures.

Table 2. Rate constants of rate-determining step $[PBC] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[H^+] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Temp. (K)	k (s^{-1})
298	1.87
303	2.13
308	2.51
313	4.47

The following intimate mechanism was proposed,

where, R = $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{NH}_3^+)\text{COOH}$

Experimental

A standard solution of L-cysteine was prepared by using double distilled water. The other chemicals used

were PBC, chromium(III), perchloric acid and NaClO_4 . All chemicals used were analytical reagent (AR) grade. 0.01 mol dm^{-3} PBC and 5.0 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid solutions were prepared. Solutions of desired concentration were prepared from this stock by suitable dilution.

The reaction was initiated by mixing a calculated amount of PBC to a mixture of L-cysteine, perchloric acid at a constant temperature of $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of PBC at 350 nm using Milton Roy 1201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm silica cells.

The temperature is kept constant using a SISKIN JULABO V constant temperature liquid circulatory bath. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k' were calculated from the plots of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ versus time. The reproducibility of rate constants obtained was $\pm 4.6\%$.

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